

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF HYGROTHERMAL AGING ON FATIGUE OF A NATURAL FIBER COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The exposition of thermoplastic composites reinforced with natural fibers to moisture is likely to lower their mechanical properties and restrain their use in the design of parts. The present work is focused on investigating the effects of hygrothermal aging on the quasi-static and fatigue behavior of a polyethylene composite reinforced with 40% wt of short birch fibers. Moreover, kinetics of isothermal moisture absorption has been studied for immersion in water at 60°C and experimental results show that moisture absorption in this type of composite material is Fickian.

1 INTRODUCTION

Engineering applications show a growing interest in composite materials. They represent an essential ingredient in the design process in many sectors, including automotive, marine and aircraft industries. Over the past decade, there has been an increased demand for “green” or natural-fiber-reinforced composites. Natural fibers provide many advantages over synthetic fibers, including low density, reasonable mechanical properties, and environmental benefits. However, the range of applications involving natural fiber composites in engineering design is still limited, due to a lack of understanding of the long-term behavior of these materials, especially under cyclic loading. Furthermore, natural fibers tend to absorb moisture from air or direct contact with water (or other liquids) due to their hydrophilic nature. These fibers are mainly composed of three constituents: cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin [1]. Cellulose is the main constituent of most natural fibers, and it is also the component responsible for its excellent structural properties. Cellulose is also hydrophilic, and it is the main cause of water uptake in this type of fibers. Hemicellulose is an amorphous polysaccharide, and it is partially soluble in water. Finally, lignin is a complex polymer which acts as a binder for the other components (cellulose, hemicellulose and others) in natural fibers and it is considered as a hydrophobic component.

For thermoplastic composites reinforced with short wood fibers, several studies have been focused on assessing their static mechanical properties in different contexts [2-9]. However, at this point, no work has been done towards assessing the effect of hygrothermal aging on fatigue.

In the work presented here, hygrothermal aging was done through immersion of specimens in water. Then, experiments were performed on short wood fibers-reinforced thermoplastic composites

under quasi-static and cyclic loading. Quasi-static tests were conducted with unaged and aged specimens to determine the effect of moisture on their mechanical properties. At this point, fatigue tests were only done with unaged specimens to evaluate the fatigue behavior of this composite material.

2 MATERIALS

The thermoplastic used, in this work, was the HDPE (Sclair 2909) donated by NOVA Chemicals. Short wood fibers from yellow birch (TMP 20-60 mesh) were also used with the HDPE to manufacture composite specimens. They were prepared in Centre for Research on Lignocellulosic Materials (CRML), in Trois-Rivières. The aspect ratio classes (length-to-diameter ratio, L/D) of the fibers were obtained by mechanical refining and screening and characterized with a fiber quality analyzer (FQA). Table 1 presents the results given by FQA and the tensile modulus of birch fibers. MAPE (maleated polyethylene, G2010) was used as a coupling agent in the composite material to improve the quality of the interface between HDPE and birch fibers.

Table 1: Mechanical properties and FQA of birch fibers [9]

Parameters	Unit	Values
L	[mm]	0.49
D	[μm]	24.7
L/ D	–	19.79
Tensile modulus	[GPa]	13.9

3 SAMPLES MANUFACTURING

Bending specimens were manufactured using 40% (in weight) of short birch fibers, 3% of MAPE and 57% of HDPE, according to the dimensions and geometry that are specified in ASTM-D638 and ASTM-D790 standards.

The manufacturing process involves two consecutive steps, which are blending and molding. Blending consists in melting polyethylene with the coupling agent on rollers at a temperature between 170 and 190 °C and mixing them with fibers during 7 minutes at 60 r.min⁻¹. After mixing all constituents, the peeling of mixture from the roller is done before re-blending it five times every 3 minutes. The aim of peeling and subsequent re-blending of the mixture is to ensure isotropy and homogeneity of the composite sheet. When blending is completed, the composite sheet is removed from the roller and it is cut into strips (using a knife) according to the molder size. Then, molding consists in putting a mold, which is filled with material, in a thermopress at 170°C and at a pressure of 10 to 15 metric tons. After 10 to 15 minutes of thermic compression, the mold is cooled below 100°C, by circulating cold water, with 43°C.min⁻¹ as constant cooling rate.

Figure 1: Samples manufacturing machine

Figure 2: Manufactured bending specimen

4 EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

4.1 Validation process

Once samples manufactured, a validation process was defined and used to select specimens that show the best and the most constant distribution and rate of short wood fibers. This validation process is based on two steps: the first step consists in conducting bending tests. These tests are based on applying a given value for bending displacement and comparing the corresponding experimental load (in this state of bending) with the theoretical load, as calculated using the ASTM-D7264 standard. The imposed value for bending displacement must keep deformation in the linear elastic range to avoid damage of specimen during these validation tests. The second validation step consists in measuring the elastic tensile modulus of specimens, using a non-destructive method (impulse excitation measurements ASTM E-1876-09) and comparing values obtained with a reference mean value of this modulus, as obtained by Alencar et al [8]. In this validation, the maximum accepted difference between theoretical and measured loads or modulus is 7% because of the huge variety of fibers distribution in each specimen.

4.2 Hygrothermal aging

Hygrothermal aging tests were conducted by immersing specimens in distilled water at 60°C. Every 48 hours, the weight and the elastic tensile modulus were measured, respectively using a balance which has an accuracy of 10⁻³ g and acoustic impulsion devices. When the specimens reached saturation, they were placed in an oven, at 65°C, until recovering their initial weight. Then, we performed flexural tests after immersion and drying.

Figure 3: Thermal bath with specimens in distilled water at 60°C

4.3 Bending tests

3-point flexural tests were performed in accordance with ASTM-D790. These tests were carried out on an Instron model LM-U150 electromechanical testing machine, equipped with a 10 kN load cell. The parameters used for these tests were 1 mm/min of speed and 55 mm of distance between the

flexural supports. The objective of these bending tests is to assess quasi-static properties of the composite (polyethylene reinforced with 40% in weight of short birch fibers) before and after hygrothermal aging.

4.4 Fatigue tests

Bending fatigue tests were conducted using a MTS servo hydraulic testing machine. They were performed by controlling the displacement with frequency and ratio of displacement respectively equal to 15 Hz and 0. Five displacement levels were used and four tests were conducted at each level to calculate a mean value for the number of cycles to failure. These displacement levels were chosen based on properties that were determined from quasi-static bending tests. A CCD camera has also been used to assess the different stages of fatigue and to determine the number of cycles to failure (Nr). At this point, these bending fatigue tests were conducted on unaged specimens to determine the fatigue behavior of the composite material before hygrothermal aging.

Figure 4: Experimental fatigue devices and positioning specimen

5 RESULTS

5.1 Hygrothermal aging

By measuring the weight of specimens at every 48h of immersion, we determined the evolution of the relative weight gain $M(t)$ as presented in figure 5 for all samples along immersion. The relative weight gain $M(t)$ is calculated using equation 1 [10].

$$M(t) = \frac{m(t) - m_0}{m_0} \quad (1)$$

where $m(t)$ and m_0 respectively represent the specimen's weight along moisture absorption and the specimen's weight before immersion.

The evolution of the relative weight gain according to the square root of immersion time, as showed in figure 5, presents three principal stages: the first stage is linear and its slope characterizes the velocity of moisture diffusion inside the specimen. This type of diffusion is called Fick's diffusion [11] and the associated diffusion coefficient D is calculated using the equation 2 [12]. Concerning the second and the third stages, they respectively represent the transition and saturation steps.

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_{sat}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

All hygrothermal aging results are summarized in table 2. The relative standard deviation, which is calculated as the ratio between the standard deviation and the mean value, is 1% for the relative weight

gain at saturation M_{sat} and 7% for the diffusion coefficient D . These percentages show that the validation process presented in section 4.1, which was done after specimens manufacturing, allows us to select samples featuring a rate and distribution of short birch fibers that is nearly constant.

Figure 5: Moisture content over the square root of time for samples immersed in water at 60°C

Table 2: Relative weight gain at saturation and diffusion coefficient of samples in the distilled water

T (°C)	Specimen	$M_{sat}(\%)$	Diffusion coefficient (mm ² /day)
60	L-3-9	10,24	$6,87 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-4-4	9,92	$6,72 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-4-5	9,92	$7,35 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-4-12	9,93	$7,09 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-4-14	9,92	$7,19 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-4-15	9,94	$7,73 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-5-5	9,95	$7,37 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-5-8	9,82	$6,86 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-5-9	9,89	$7,35 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-5-10	9,98	$8,58 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-5-13	9,94	$7,35 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	L-5-14	9,89	$7,18 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	Mean value	9,95	$7,3 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	STD DEV	0,1	$4,9 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	Ratio	0,01	0,07

During these hygrothermal aging tests, we used an acoustic impulsion device to determine the evolution of elastic tensile modulus along immersion. Figure 6a and 6b respectively present the evolution of tensile modulus for each aged samples and the mean evolution of this modulus with the associated standard deviation. According to figure 6b the mean modulus decreases from 4.53 GPa to 2.14 GPa during the first 528 hours. After this period, it remains nearly constant (the maximum relative standard deviation is 4.16%). As expected, the presence of moisture decreases the stiffness (tensile modulus) of this composite (polyethylene reinforced with 40% in weight of short birch fibers).

Figure 6: Elastic tensile modulus over the square root of time: a) Evolution of elastic tensile modulus for each sample immersed in water; b) Evolution of mean tensile modulus

5.2 Bending tests

Figure 7 presents quasi static bending stress-strain curves obtained for specimens, before and after immersion.

Unaged samples present 49.76 MPa of mean maximum stress and 5.55 % of mean failure strain. The presence of moisture in specimens, after hygrothermal aging, causes a 44.43% decrease of the maximum stress and a 80.18% increase of the failure strain.

The mechanical properties obtained from all these bending tests are summarized in table 3.

Figure 7: Bending testing curves for aged and unaged HDPE/40% wt of short birch fibers

Table 3: Mechanical properties of unaged and aged samples

Specimen	Elastic bending modulus (GPa)	Maximum stress (MPa)	Failure strain (%)
Unaged specimen L-7-1	2,36	52,19	5,87
Unaged specimen L-6-8	2,32	47,33	5,22
Mean value	2,34	49,76	5,55
STD DEV	0,03	3,44	0,46
Ratio	0,01	0,07	0,08
Wet specimen	1,37	27,65	10

5.3 Fatigue tests

As introduced above, at this point, fatigue bending tests were only conducted on unaged specimens. From these tests, the number of cycles to failure (Nr) was determined at each displacement level (between 1.2 and 2 mm). Figure 8 show that Nr decreases with the increase of displacement level between 1.2 and 2 mm. Decrease is 87.29% at 2mm if compared to the number of cycles to failure at 1.2 mm. All these preliminary results are summarized in table 4.

Figure 8: Number of cycles to failure for each displacement level

Table 4: Number of cycles to failure for each displacement level

Displacement level (mm)	Displacement level compared to the displacement at failure (%)	N_r (cycles)
1,2	14,74	$N_r > 10^6$
1,4	17,2	$9,78 \cdot 10^5$
1,6	19,66	$5,38 \cdot 10^5$
1,84	22,6	$1,84 \cdot 10^5$
2	24,57	$1,27 \cdot 10^5$

As mentioned previously, a CCD camera has been used during these fatigue tests. The objective is not only to determine the number of cycles to failure, but also to identify phenomenon occurring along the different stages of fatigue for this composite material. Figure 9 presents these stages of fatigue as shown by the camera.

e)

Figure 9: Fatigue stages detected by CCD camera with 1.84 mm of maximum displacement and 15 Hz of frequency: a) Crack initiation and propagation ($1,74 \cdot 10^5$); b) Zoom on boxed area; c) Crack evolution ($1,83 \cdot 10^5$); d) Zoom on boxed area; e) Failure of specimen ($1,84 \cdot 10^5$)

6 FUTURE WORKS

The immediate extension of this work is performing bending fatigue tests on both unaged and aged specimens to assess the influence of moisture diffusion on the fatigue behavior of this composite. Aged specimens will be dried in an oven at 65°C. During these tests, acoustic emission sensors will be used to study the physical phenomenon and damage mechanisms of composite material [8].

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this contribution, immersion tests in an isothermal bath, filled with distilled water at 60°C, have been conducted on a polyethylene composite, reinforced with 40% (in weight) of short birch fibers. It appears that the absorption process is always Fickian, since the first stage of diffusion over the square root of time is clearly linear. Experimental results outcome from these tests showed that the mean diffusion coefficient and the mean relative weight gain at saturation are respectively equal to $7,3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mm²/day and 9.95 %. Also, measurement of the elastic tensile modulus along immersion, using an acoustic impulsion device, showed that the mean modulus decreases from 4.53 GPa to 2.14 GPa during the first 528 hours of immersion. After this period, it remains nearly constant, with 4.16% of maximum relative standard deviation. Quasi-static and fatigue bending tests were also conducted. Quasi-static bending tests showed a 44.43% decrease of the maximum stress and a 80.18% increase of the failure strain between unaged and aged (at saturation) specimens. Fatigue experiments were performed, using five displacement levels, on unaged samples. These experiments showed a 87.29% decrease of the number of cycles to failure (N_r) between 1.2 mm and 2 mm displacement levels.

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